

RESTORE

Renewable Energy based seasonal Storage
Technology in Order to Raise Economic and
environmental sustainability of DHC

D7.6 - Project Website and Social Media Accounts

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PROJECT INFORMATION SHEET	
Project Acronym	RESTORE
Project Full Title	Renewable Energy based seasonal Storage Technology in Order to Raise Environmental sustainability of DHC
Grant Agreement	101036766
Call Identifier	H2020-LC-GD-2020-1
Topic	Innovative land-based and offshore renewable energy technologies and their integration into the energy system
Project Duration	48 months (October 2021 – September 2025)
Project Website	www.restore-dhc.eu
Disclaimer	The sole responsibility for the content of this document lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the funding authorities. The funding authorities are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION SHEET	
Number	Deliverable D7.6
Full Title	Project Website and Social Media Accounts
Related WP	WP7 (RESTORE Communication, Dissemination and Community Building)
Related Task	Task 7.2 (RESTORE Dissemination & Communication Tools and Channels)
Lead Beneficiary	SIG Solites
Author(s)	Thomas Schmidt (SIG Solites) – schmidt@solites.de
Contributor(s)	All partners
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QUALITY CONTROL ASSESSMENT SHEET			
ISSUE	DATE	COMMENT	AUTHOR
V0.1	20/01/2022	Draft	Thomas Schmidt (SIG Solites) Task Leader
V0.2	31/01/2022	Review	All partners
V1.0	01/02/2022	Submission to the EC	Francisco Cabello Nuñez (CENER) Coordinator
V1.1	15/02/2022	Re-submission to the EC (according PO comments)	Francisco Cabello Nuñez (CENER) Coordinator
V1.2	16/02/2022	Re-submission to the EC	Francisco Cabello Nuñez (CENER) Coordinator
V1.3	11/03/2022	Re-submission to the EC	Francisco Cabello Nuñez (CENER) Coordinator

Summary

This document briefly describes the following RESTORE online-deliverables:

1. RESTORE Website, see www.restore-dhc.eu
2. RESTORE Twitter Social Media Account, see https://twitter.com/restore_dhc
3. RESTORE LinkedIn Social Media Account, see <https://www.linkedin.com/company/restore-dhc-project>

The status of the online-deliverables described in this document is the status of the first versions after setup. They have however to be considered as “living” deliverables, this means contents will continuously updated and kept up to date and active during the project period.

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1. Project website

The RESTORE Project Website is available at the web address (see also Figure 1):

www.restore-dhc.eu

The main page (Home) shows a welcome page followed by some selected content that is also available in other parts of the website structure and a footer section with a navigation bar, EU reference and disclaimer (see Figure 2).

Figure 1: Screenshot of the RESTORE website welcome page

Figure 2: Screenshot of the footer of the main page

The main menu of the website contains the following main and sub sections:

Main section	Sub section
Home	
About RESTORE	RESTORE Technology Reversible Organic Rankine Cycle Thermo-Chemical Energy Storage Virtual Use Cases
Resources	Publications Links
News & Events	News Events Newsletter
About us	H2020 RESTORE Partners Contact & Imprint Data Protection

The sections “About RESTORE” and “About Us” give an overview of the main technical approach and objectives of the RESTORE project as well as the involved partner institutions. In the sections “Resources” and “News & Events” the outcomes of the project will be published regularly during the project period. For further details on the content please refer to the website.

For an evaluation of the website (number of visitors etc.) the web analytics tool Matomo (www.matomo.org) is used.

2. Social Media Accounts

Social media accounts for the platforms Twitter and LinkedIn have been created, see Figure 3. These channels will be linked to other relevant projects and the RESTORE target groups in the near future. They are developed into active communication channels to the target audiences to provide easy and direct access and encourage engagement.

The corresponding access addresses are:

Twitter: https://twitter.com/restore_dhc

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/restore-dhc-project>.

Figure 3: Screenshots of Twitter (left) and LinkedIn (right) pages